

THE EFFECTS OF DIFFERENCES IN THERMAL COEFFICIENTS OF
EXPANSION IN SiC WHISKER 6061 ALUMINUM COMPOSITE*

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Summary

When a metal matrix composite is cooled down to room temperature from the fabrication or annealing temperature, residual stresses are induced in the composite due to the mismatch of the thermal expansion coefficients between the matrix and whisker.

An investigation was undertaken of the extent of the thermal residual stresses by an X-ray diffraction technique as well as of the difference of the yield stresses $\Delta\sigma_y$ between tension and compression resulting from the thermal residual stresses. A theoretical model based on the Eshelby's method was then constructed for the prediction of the thermal residual stresses and $\Delta\sigma_y$. The agreement obtained was very good between the experimental results and the theoretical predictions.

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Introduction

Metal matrix composites (MMCs), including eutectic composites, are becoming important in their application to structural components which are to be used at intermediate and high temperatures. When MMCs are fabricated at high temperature or annealed at a certain high temperature and cooled down to room temperature, undesirable results, such as low tensile yield stress and strength of the MMC upon mechanical testing at room temperature, are produced. These results are mainly due to residual stresses that are caused by the mismatch of the thermal expansion coefficients between the matrix and fiber. This subject has been studied by a number of researchers (for examples see references 1-13). The residual stresses so induced have been observed in tungsten fiber/copper composites⁽⁷⁾ and in SiC whisker/6061 Al composites^(8,9). Most of the models purposed to estimate the residual stress were based on one-dimensional analysis⁽¹⁻³⁾, continuous fiber system^(4,5), or spherical particle system⁽¹⁰⁾.

The model based on Eshelby's equivalent inclusion method⁽⁷⁾ has been used to solve the problem of thermal residual stress⁽¹²⁻¹⁴⁾. The advantages of the Eshelby's model are that it can solve a three-dimensional composite system such as short whisker composite and also can take into account the effect of the volume fraction of whisker (V_w) easily.

Eshelby's method has been used also for predicting the yield stress and work-hardening rate of metal matrix composites⁽¹⁵⁻¹⁹⁾. The effect of the thermally induced residual stress on the yield stresses has been discussed by Wakashima et al.⁽¹⁸⁾ who predicted that the yield stress in compression (σ_y^c) exceeds that in tension (σ_y^t) for continuous B fiber/Al composites which were cooled down, although no comparison with the experimental data was made.

In this paper we focus on the residual stresses induced in a short whisker MMC due to the temperature drop and its effect on the yield stresses. The target short whisker MMC is SiC whisker/6061 Al composite.

Experimental Procedure

Materials

The target short fiber MMC was SiC whisker/6061 Al composite and was purchased from ARCO/SILAG. The composite was in the form of an extruded rod 15.5 mm in diameter. Three different volume fractions of whisker (V_w) were used: $V_w = 0, 0.05$ and 0.2 . The composite was supplied as-fabricated (no heat treatment made), was machined into samples (Fig. 1a and 1b), annealed for 12 hours at 810 K, and then furnace cooled.

Testing Methods

Tension and Compression Tests. The testing was performed in an Instron testing machine using a liquid metal container as the lower gripping device. This method of gripping was employed to ensure very good alignment of the sample. This test procedure is described in greater detail elsewhere⁽²⁰⁾. Samples of two different gauge lengths were used to determine if there was a gauge length effect (there was none). The effective gauge length of the

samples was determined by glueing strain gauges on the center portion of the sample and comparing the results obtained from a clip on an extensometer which mounted into the "V" grooves. If the extensometer is mounted directly to the uniform gauge section, there is a high probability that the sample will fracture where the "knife" edge of the extensometer makes contact with the sample. Several tests in the low stress range were conducted using both the extensometer and the strain gauge; from these tests the effective gauge length was determined. Subsequent tests were conducted using only the extensometer. The samples, which were tested in the range from $8 \times 10^{-5} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ to $2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ sec}^{-1}$, showed no effect on strain rate.

Figure 1 - A schematic diagram of the sample configuration which was used in the tension and compression testing. The dimensions are in millimeters.

Residual Stress Measurement by X-ray Diffraction. The X-ray diffraction technique was used to measure residual stress. Two components of the residual stress were focused on: the stress along the extrusion direction (longitudinal direction), which coincides with the whisker axis of a majority of whiskers (σ_L), and the one in the transverse direction (σ_T). The data were obtained and reduced by standard techniques as outlined by Cohen et al.⁽²¹⁾.

Experimental Results

The stress-strain curves of $V_w = 0, 0.05$ and 0.2 composites are plotted in Fig. 2a, 2b, and 2c, respectively. The solid and dashed curves denote the tensile and compressive test results, respectively. The yield stress was measured as 0.2% off set strain and is indicated in the figures by arrows.

Figure 2a - The absolute stress vs. strain curves for tension and compression test of 0 volume % whisker material in the annealed condition.

Figure 2b - The absolute value of stress vs. strain for 5 volume % whisker composite in the annealed condition.

Figure 2c - The absolute value of the stress as a function of strain for 20 volume % whisker material in the annealed condition.

The residual stresses were measured by X-ray diffraction on three different values of V_w (0, 0.05, and 0.2) and are tabulated in Table I where the range of scattered data is also shown. It is noted that the values of σ_L and σ_T represent the volume average quantity in the matrix (6061 Al). It should also be noted that a compressive residual stress was found for all cases.

Table I
Residual Stresses X-Ray Determination

Sample Designation V_w %	Trans. σ_T MPa	Long. σ_L MPa
0	-37 to -44	-18 to -22
5	-17 to -41.4	-29 to -41.4
20	-49 to -57.3	-24 to -44.2

- compressive residual stress

Theoretical Procedure

The theoretical model used here is based on Eshelby's equivalent inclusion model. Mori and his co-workers⁽¹⁵⁻¹⁷⁾ extended Eshelby's method to predict the yield stress (σ_y) and work-hardening rate of aligned short whisker composites. Wakashima et al.⁽¹⁸⁾ extended the above approach to predict σ_y by considering the mismatch of the thermal expansion coefficients of the matrix and fiber. Following the above models, Takao and Taya⁽¹⁴⁾

have recently computed the stress field in and around a short fiber in a short fiber composite where the fiber is anisotropic both in stiffness and thermal expansion.

In this paper we focus on the average thermal residual stress induced in the matrix by the cool-down process and also the yield stresses in tension (σ_y^t) and compression (σ_y^c) when the composite is tested at the room temperature. The former case is essentially based on the model by Takao and Taya⁽¹⁴⁾, and as the latter case, we extend the model by Wakashima et al.⁽¹⁸⁾ to account for the bi-linear stress-strain curve of the matrix.

Formulation

Consider an infinite body (D) which contains ellipsoidal whiskers (Ω) aligned along the x_3 -axis (Fig. 3). This composite body D is subjected to the applied stress field σ_{ij}^o . The stiffness tensors of the matrix (D- Ω) and whisker (Ω) are denoted by C_{ijkl} and C_{ijkl}^w , respectively. Following Eshelby, the transformation strain⁽¹¹⁾ or eigenstrain⁽²²⁾ is given in

the fiber domain Ω as α_{ij}^* , where α_{ij}^* is the strain due to the mismatch of the thermal expansion coefficients and the uniform plastic strain e_{ij}^p is prescribed in the matrix⁽¹⁵⁾. As far as the stress field is concerned, the model of Fig. 4 is equivalent to that of Fig. 3. Thus, the present problem is reduced to "inhomogeneous inclusions problem" (Fig. 4)⁽²²⁾. The model of Fig. 4 will be used not only to predict the yield stresses and work-hardening rate, but also to compute the thermal residual stress. For in the latter case, we will set $\sigma_{ij}^o = e_{ij}^p = 0$.

Figure 3 - Theoretical model; actual case

Figure 4 - The equivalent inclusion model converted from Figure 3.

Following the Eshelby's equivalent inclusion method modified for a finite volume fraction of whiskers^(22,23), the total stress field in the fibers $\sigma_{ij}^0 + \sigma_{ij}$ is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{ij}^0 + \sigma_{ij} &= C_{ijkl}^w \{e_{kl}^0 + \tilde{e}_{kl} + e_{kl} - (\alpha_{kl}^* - e_{kl}^p)\} \\ &= C_{ijkl} \{e_{kl}^0 + \tilde{e}_{kl} + e_{kl} - (\alpha_{kl}^* - e_{kl}^p) - e_{kl}^*\} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where

$$\sigma_{ij}^0 = C_{ijkl} e_{kl}^0 \quad \text{in } D \quad (2)$$

$$\langle \sigma_{ij} \rangle_m = C_{ijkl} \tilde{e}_{kl} \quad \text{in } D-\Omega \quad (3)$$

In Eq. (1), e_{kle}^* is the fictitious eigenstrain⁽²²⁾ which was introduced to connect the present problem to "inclusion problem" and \tilde{e}_{ij} is the average strain disturbance in the matrix and related to the average stress disturbance in the matrix $\langle \sigma_{ij} \rangle_m$ by Eq. (3). $\langle \sigma_{ij} \rangle_m$ is defined by

$$\langle \sigma_{ij} \rangle_m = \frac{1}{V_{D-\Omega}} \int_{D-\Omega} \sigma_{ij} dv \quad (4)$$

where $V_{D-\Omega}$ is the total volume of the matrix and σ_{ij} , and e_{ij} in Eqs. (1) and (4) is the stress and strain disturbance, respectively, by a single fiber Ω when it is embedded in an infinite matrix. Since the stress disturbance when it is integrated in the entire domain D vanishes,

$$\int_D \sigma_{ij} dv = 0 \quad (5)$$

The stress disturbance σ_{ij} is obtained from Eqs. (1) and (2)

$$\sigma_{ij} = C_{ijkl} (\tilde{e}_{kl} + e_{kl} - e_{kl}^{**}) \quad (6)$$

where

$$e_{kl}^{**} = \alpha_{kl}^* + e_{kl}^* - e_{kl}^p \quad (7)$$

From Eqs. (3), (5) and (6), we obtain

$$\tilde{e}_{ij} = -V_w (e_{ij} - e_{ij}^{**}) \quad (8)$$

According to Eshelby, e_{ij} is related to the total eigenstrain e_{kl}^{**} as

$$e_{ij} = S_{ijkl} e_{kl}^{**} \quad (9)$$

where S_{ijke} is the Eshelby's tensor and a function of C_{ijkl} , C_{ijkl}^w and the geometry of the ellipsoidal whisker⁽²²⁾. The fiber is assumed as a prolate spheroid, hence the whisker aspect ratio l/d is a single geometrical parameter. For simplicity, we assume that the matrix and fiber are isotropic both in stiffness and thermal expansion coefficient. Thus, C_{ijkl} , C_{ijkl}^w and α_{ij}^* are given by

$$C_{ijkl} = \lambda \delta_{ij} \delta_{kl} + \mu (\delta_{ik} \delta_{jl} + \delta_{il} \delta_{kj}) \quad (10)$$

$$C_{ijkl}^w = \lambda^w \delta_{ij} \delta_{kl} + \mu^w (\delta_{ik} \delta_{jl} + \delta_{il} \delta_{kj}) \quad (11)$$

$$\alpha_{ij}^* = -(\alpha_w - \alpha) \delta_{ij} \Delta T \quad (12)$$

In the above equations, δ_{ij} is the Kronecker's delta, λ (λ^w) and μ (μ^w) are Lamé's constants of the matrix (whisker), α (α_w) is the thermal expansion coefficient of the matrix (fiber) and ΔT is the change in temperature ($\Delta T > 0$ corresponds to the temperature drop).

The stress field in the fiber is obtained from Eqs. (6), (8), (9) and (10)

$$\sigma_{ij} = (1 - V_w) \{ (S_{kkmn}^{**} e_{mn}^{**} - e_{kk}^{**}) \lambda \delta_{ij} + 2\mu (S_{ijmn}^{**} e_{mn}^{**} - e_{ij}^{**}) \} \quad (13)$$

After solving for e_{ij}^{**} in Eq. (1) by use of Eqs. (8) and (9), we can compute the stress disturbance σ_{ij} in the whisker from Eq. (13).

Yield Stresses σ_y^t , σ_y^c and Work-Hardening Rate

The method of computing the yield stresses σ_y^t and σ_y^c and the work-hardening rate of the composite is described briefly. The total potential energy of Fig. 3, U, is given by

$$U = \frac{1}{2} \int_D (\sigma_{ij}^o + \sigma_{ij}) (u_{ij}^o + \tilde{u}_{ij} + u_{ij} - e_{ij}^p - \alpha_{ij}^*) dV - \int_{|D|} \sigma_{ij}^o n_j (u_i^o + \tilde{u}_i + u_i) dS \quad (14)$$

where u_i^o , \tilde{u}_i and u_i are the displacement components corresponding to e_{ij}^o , \tilde{e}_{ij} and e_{ij} , respectively; the index j preceded by a comma denotes a partial differentiation with respect to x_j ; |D| is the boundary of D; and n_j is the j-th component of a unit vector outer normal to |D|. Then, the change in u due to the change in the plastic strain δe_{ij}^p is given by

$$\delta U = - \int_D (\sigma_{ij}^o + \sigma_{ij}) \delta e_{ij}^p dV \quad (15)$$

In the above deviation, the Gauss' divergence theory and the following equation were used

$$\int_D \sigma_{ij} (\delta \tilde{u}_{ij} + \delta u_{ij}) dV = 0$$

Noting that the plastic strain exists only in the matrix (D- Ω), Eq. (15) is reduced to

$$\delta U = - \delta e_{ij}^p \{ (1 - V_w) \sigma_{ij}^o - V_w \sigma_{ij} \} \quad (16)$$

Under the uniaxial stress along the x_3 -axis (σ_o), σ_{ij}^o and e_{ij}^p are given by

$$\sigma_{ij}^o = \begin{matrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ \sigma_o \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{matrix} \quad e_{ij}^p = \begin{matrix} -1/2e_p \\ -1/2e_p \\ e_p \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{matrix} \quad (17)$$

where the six components of σ_{ij}^o and e_{ij}^p are expressed in the order of (ij) = 11, 22, 33, 23, 31, and 12, and e_p is the plastic strain along the x_3 -axis. On the other hand, the energy dissipation due to the plastic work in the matrix, δQ , is given by

$$\delta Q = (1 - V_w) \sigma_y \delta e_p \quad (18)$$

where σ_y is the flow stress of the matrix for the bilinear model

$$\sigma_y = \sigma_y^o + E_T(e - e_p) \quad (19)$$

where σ_y^o and E_T are the initial yield stress and tangent, modulus of the matrix, respectively, and e is the total strain. Since $\delta U + \delta O = 0$, we obtain

$$\sigma_o = \sigma_y + \frac{V_w}{(1-V_w)} (\sigma_{33} - \sigma_{11}) \quad (20)$$

In the above deviation, $\sigma_{11} - \sigma_{22}$, $e_{11}^p = e_{22}^p = -\frac{1}{2} e_p$ were used. Combining the solutions of σ_{ij} in Eq. (13) and Eq. (20), we can obtain the yield stress of the composite in tension ($\sigma_y^t = \sigma_o$) and that in compression ($\sigma_y^c = \sigma_o$) as

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_y^t / \sigma_y^o &= C_0 + C_1 \alpha_m \Delta T \\ \sigma_y^c / \sigma_y^o &= C_0 - C_1 \alpha_m \Delta T \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

Similarly, the work-hardening rate of the composite, \bar{E}_T is obtained as

$$\bar{E}_T / E_T = C_2 + C_3 \left(\frac{E_T}{E} \right) \quad (22)$$

In the above equations, C_0 , C_1 , C_2 , and C_3 are functions of the mechanical properties of the matrix and whisker and the fiber aspect l/d , E is the Young's modulus of the matrix.

Thermal Residual Stress

When the composite is cooled down by ΔT , the thermal residual stress is induced in the composite. The theoretical model for this problem is the same as that shown in Fig. 4 except that $\sigma_{ij}^o = e_{ij}^p = 0$ in the present case. Hence, the formulation up to Eq. (13) is valid and will be used to compute the thermal residual stress. Once the stress within the whisker $\sigma_{ij}^{(in)}$ is computed, the stresses just outside the whisker $\sigma_{ij}^{(out)}$ can be obtained by the following relation⁽¹³⁾

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{pq}^{(out)} &= \sigma_{pq}^{(in)} + C_{pqmn} \left\{ - C_{klij} e_{ij}^{**} n_i n_j n_k n_l \frac{(\lambda+2\mu)\delta_{km} - (\lambda+\mu)n_k n_m}{\mu(\lambda+2\mu)} \right. \\ &\quad \left. + e_{mn}^{**} \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

where $\sigma_{pq}^{(in)}$ is given by Eq. (13), e_{ij}^{**} is solved by Eq. (1), λ and μ are previously defined and n_i is the i -th component of the unit vector perpendicular to the surface of the whisker. If one wants to compute the stresses just outside the equator of the ellipsoidal whisker where $n = (1, 0, 0)$, we can obtain the stresses in polar coordinates, σ_r , σ_θ and σ_z there as

$$\begin{aligned}
\sigma_r^{(out)} &= \sigma_r^{(in)} \\
\sigma_\theta^{(out)} &= \sigma_\theta^{(in)} + 2\mu \left\{ \frac{1}{1-\nu} e_{11}^{**} + \frac{\nu}{1-\nu} e_{33}^{**} \right\} \\
\sigma_z^{(out)} &= \sigma_z^{(in)} + 2\mu \left\{ \frac{\nu}{1-\nu} e_{11}^{**} + \frac{1}{1-\nu} e_{33}^{**} \right\}
\end{aligned} \tag{24}$$

where ν is the Poisson's ratio of the matrix.

Next the average stress field in the matrix, $\langle \sigma_{ij} \rangle_m$, can be also obtained from Eqs. (3), (8) and (9) as

$$\langle \sigma_{ij} \rangle_m = -V_w C_{ijkl} (S_{klmn} e_{mn}^{**} - e_{kl}^{**}) \tag{25}$$

The average stress in the matrix, $\langle \sigma_r \rangle_m$, $\langle \sigma_\theta \rangle_m$ and $\langle \sigma_z \rangle_m$, will be computed by setting $ij = 11, 22$, and 33 in Eq. (25). It should be noted here that $\langle \sigma_r \rangle_m = \langle \sigma_\theta \rangle_m$ due to the assumptions of an aligned short whisker composite which results in the transverse isotropy of the volume average quantity.

Theoretical Results

The thermo-mechanical data of the matrix and whisker for the theoretical calculations are obtained from the stress-strain curve of the matrix (Fig. 2a) and the material properties handbook.

Annealed 6061 Al matrix (bilinear model):

$$\begin{aligned}
E &= 47.5 \text{ GPa} \\
E_T &= 2.3 \text{ GPa} \\
\sigma_y^0 &= 47.5 \text{ MPa} \\
\nu &= 0.33 \\
\alpha &= 23.6 \times 10^{-6}/^\circ\text{C}
\end{aligned} \tag{26}$$

SiC Whisker:

$$\begin{aligned}
E_w &= 427 \text{ GPa} \\
\nu_w &= 0.17 \\
\alpha_w &= 4.3 \times 10^{-6}/^\circ\text{C} \\
\ell/d &= 1.8
\end{aligned} \tag{27}$$

where the average value of the fiber aspect ratio (ℓ/d) was used⁽²⁴⁾ and the bilinear stress strain curve of the matrix is indicated by a dash-dot line in Fig. 2a. The temperature drop ΔT is defined as

$$\Delta T = T_1 - T_0 \tag{28}$$

where T_1 is taken as the temperature below which dislocation generation is minimal during the cooling process⁽⁹⁾ and T_0 is the room temperature. Thus, for the present composite system ΔT is set equal to 200 K.

The theoretically predicted σ_y^c and σ_y^t can be obtained from Eq. (21). The differences between σ_y^c and σ_y^t ($\sigma_y^c - \sigma_y^t$) for various V_w are shown as the solid line in Fig. 5. The differences between σ_y^c and σ_y^t increase with increasing V_w . The experimentally determined differences between σ_y^c and σ_y^t are represented by the open circles in Fig. 5. The experimental values of the yield stresses are taken as the stresses 0.2% off-set strain. It follows (Fig. 5) that good agreement is obtained between the experimental

Figure 5 - The difference in yield stress between compression and tension as a function of volume % silicon carbide whisker.

and theoretical results of the difference in the compressive tensile yield stresses. However, the experimental values of σ_y^c are greater than the theoretical values of σ_y^c , and similarly the experimental values of σ_y^t are greater than the theoretical values of σ_y^t .

From the data given by Eqs. (26) - (27) and the use of Eq. (25), we have computed the average stresses in the matrix and the stresses just outside the fiber and plotted schematically the σ_L and $\langle \sigma_L \rangle_m$ along the x (or x_2) and x_3 axes in Fig. 6.

Figure 6 - Is a schematic of the stress distribution in the matrix and in the reinforcement due to the difference in thermal coefficient of expansion between the silicon-carbide and aluminum.

Next, the thermal residual stresses averaged in the matrix of the SiC whisker/6061 Al are predicted by Eq. (25) and the results on $\langle \sigma_m \rangle_T$ and $\langle \sigma_L \rangle_m$ are plotted in Fig. 7 as a function of the volume fraction of whisker (V_w), where the subscripts, T and L denote the component along the transverse direction (r and θ) and longitudinal direction (z). The average theoretical thermal-residual stress is predicted to be tensile in nature.

Figure 7 - Predicted residual stress in the matrix for the transverse and longitudinal directions.

Discussion and Conclusions

The theoretical predictions and experimental results are in very good agreement in most cases, and in some cases the differences are to be expected.

The theoretical model is based on an extension of previous work by Eshelby⁽¹¹⁾, Mura and Taya⁽¹³⁾, and Tanaka and Mori⁽¹⁵⁾, and it can predict the yield stress in tension and compression and the thermal residual stress. The predicted values of the yield stress in tension and compression are less than the experimentally determined values of the yield stress in tensional compression. This difference between the theoretical and experimental stresses is due to the fact that the $V_w = 0$ curves of stress vs. strain were used for the matrix in the composite cases. It has been demonstrated by Arsenault and Fisher⁽⁸⁾ and Vogelsang, et al.⁽⁹⁾ that there is a much higher dislocation density in the annealed composite matrix than in the $V_w = 0$ material. Therefore, the matrix is stronger than the annealed $V_w = 0$ matrix alloy. However, this increase in matrix strength due to a higher disloca-

tion density does not influence the difference in yield stress in the compression vs. tension. The theoretical prediction is that the yield stress in compression should be higher than the yield stress in tension, and this is exactly what is observed experimentally.

The theoretical prediction that the compressive yield stress is higher than the tensile yield stress suggests that a tensile residual stress exists in the matrix of composite. An average tensile residual stress is predicted in the matrix as shown in Figs. 6 and 7. However, the experimentally determined residual stress is compressive, i.e., opposite of the prediction. This difference can qualitatively be explained in terms of the magnitude of the tensile and compressive residual stresses in the matrix. If the compressive regions of the matrix were eliminated and only the tensile regions were examined, then there would be no change in the diffraction peak conditions, because the limit of detection is ~ 50 MPa. If a similar experiment were conducted, but in this case only the compressive regions were kept then there would be a change in peak position because the compressive residual stress is greater than the detection limit. Now, if both tensile and compressive regions are combined, the net result, a small compressive residual, will be experimentally detected, which is in agreement with the X-ray residual stress measurements.

It is possible to arrive at the following conclusions from the theoretical model and the experimental results.

1. The theoretical model predicts a higher compression yield stress than tensile yield stress, which is in agreement with the experimental results.
2. The absolute magnitude of the predicted yield stress (tensile and compressive) is less than the experimental yield stress due to an increase in matrix strengthening. The increased matrix strength is due to a higher dislocation density in the matrix; the higher dislocation density is a consequence of the difference in coefficient of thermal expansion between the Al alloy matrix and the SiC.
3. The magnitude of the average residual stress is small, but at the SiC-Al alloy interface there can be a large compressive stress.
4. The residual stress, in the region between SiC whiskers, is tensile and this is the likely region where plastic deformation would begin. For in this region the matrix contains a lower dislocation density than adjacent to the SiC whisker, i.e., in this region the matrix is weaker.

References

1. E. R. Thompson, D. A. Koss, and J. C. Chestnutt, Metall. Trans. 1 (1970), p. 2807.
2. D. A. Koss and S. M. Copley, Metall. Trans. 2 (1971), p. 1557.
3. J. K. Lees, Polymer Eng. Sci. 8 (1968), p. 195.
4. S. S. Hecker, C. H. Hamilton and L. J. Ebert, J. Mater. Sci. 5 (1970), p. 868.
5. J. Gayda and L. J. Ebert, Metall. Trans. 10A (1979), p. 349.
6. S. D. Tsai, D. Mahulikar, H. L. Marcus, I. C. Noyan and J. B. Cohen, Mater. Sci. & Eng. 47 (1981), p. 145.
7. K. K. Chawla and M. Metzger, J. Mater. Sci. 7 (1972), p. 34.
8. R. J. Arsenault and R. M. Fisher, Scripta Metall. 17 (1983), p. 67.

9. M. Vogelsang, R. J. Arsenault, and R. M. Fisher, submitted for publication.
10. J. K. Lee, Y. Y. Earmme, H. I. Aaronson and K. C. Russell, Metall. Trans. 11A (1980), p. 1837.
11. J. D. Eshelby, Proc. Roy. Soc. London A241 (1957), p. 376.
12. K. Wakashima, M. Otsuka and S. Umekawa, J. Comp. Mater. 8 (1976), p. 391.
13. T. Mura and M. Taya, Proc. of the 2nd U.S.-Japan Conf. on Comp. Mater. ASTM, under review.
14. Y. Takao and M. Taya, J. Appl. Mech., under review.
15. K. Tanaka and T. Mori, Acta Metall. 18 (1970), p. 931.
16. K. Tanaka, K. Wakashima and T. Mori, J. Mech. Phys. Solids 21 (1973), p. 207.
17. S. C. Lin, T. Mura, M. Shibata and T. Mori, Acta Metall. 21 (1973), p. 505.
18. K. Wakashima, S. Kurihara and S. Umekawa, Japan Soc. Comp. Mater. 2 (1976), p. 1.
19. A. Daimaru and M. Taya, Proc. of the 4th Intl. Conf. on Comp. Materials, Edited by Hayashi et al., Japan Soc. Comp. Materials, Tokyo (1982), p. 199.
20. R. Hsu and R. J. Arsenault, Mat. Sci. & Eng. 66 (1984), p. 35.
21. J. B. Cohen and L. Schwartz, Diffraction Methods in Materials Science, MacMillan.
22. T. Mura, Micromechanics of Defects in Solids, Martinus Nijhoff Publishers, 1982.
23. T. Mori and K. Tanaka, Acta Metall. 21 (1973), p. 571.
24. R. J. Arsenault, Mater. Sci. & Eng., 64 (1984), p. 171.